

1. F·A·A·M facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.: B119
Date: 04/08/2005
Take Off: 10:55:23
Landing: 15:54:12
Flight Time: 4h55m49

Campaign: AMPEP
Operating Area: South and East Coast, to Newcastle area

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Foster	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Alan Roberts	Directflight
3	CCM	Sue Angold	Directflight
4	Mission Scientist	Eiko Nemitz	CEH
5	Flight Manager	Alan Woolley	FAAM
6	Cloud Physics	Jim Crawford	FAAM
7	Filters	Hugh Coe	Manchester
8	Core Chemistry/CCM2/TDLAS	Doug Anderson	FAAM
9	CCN	Paul James	FAAM
10	AMS	Gerard Capes	Manchester
11	Bag sampling 1	Debbie Polson	CEH
12	Bag sampling 2	Alison Perry	FAAM
13			
14			
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Flight Track:

B119 Track 04-AUG-05

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No b119
 Date: 4/8/05
 Project: AMPEP
 Location: North Sea Coast

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
102843		inu to nav	-.01 kft	121	
104631		taxy start	-.01 kft	120	
105523		T/O	-.02 kft	212	from Cranfield
110352		asp open	10.0 kft	058	
111635	112739	Profile 1	5.7 - -.18 kft	356	
112037		Profile 1	1.8 kft	324	interrupt
112500		Profile 1	1.9 kft	329	resume
112739	112847	Run 1	-.18 - -.13 kft	336	
112847	112947	Profile 2	-.13 - 0.72 kft	334	
112947	122445	Run 2	0.72 - 0.00 kft	314	
122633	143249	Run 3	0.00 - 0.60 kft	168	
123226		dlu reset	0.80 kft	167	port fwd at ~1228
143623	143841	Run 4	0.60 - -.27 kft	089	
143943	144420	Profile 3	-.27 - 4.5 kft	090	
144421	145703	Run 5	4.6 kft	091	
150016	152449	Run 6	0.59 - 0.70 kft	006	
152607	153118	Profile 4	3.0 - 6.0 kft	274	actual start
152713		Profile 4	3.5 kft	275	interrupt
152720		Profile 4	3.9 kft	274	resumed
153350	154132	Run 7	10.0 kft	248	
154116		asp closed	10.0 kft	248	
155412		Land	0.04 kft	214	at cranfield
155743		standstill	0.06 kft	307	52'04.36N, 0'37.50W

GEOSTROPHIC WIND SCALE
IN KNOTS FOR ISOBARS AT 4 MS INTERVALS
POLAR STEREOGRAPHIC PROJECTION

B119 Track 04-AUG-05

Sortie Brief: AMPEP

Flight Number : B119

Mission Scientist: Eiko Nemitz, CEH

Date : 04-August-2005

Outline schedule:

05:00 – Power to aircraft – warm-up
07:00 – Briefing
08:15 – Clear aircraft and security check
08:30 – Doors close
09:00 – Take off Cranfield
13:45 – Land Cranfield
14:15 – Debrief
15:45 – Power down

Location: A coastal transect of the South and East Coast of England

Sortie Aims: To measure the UK pollutant budget of a range of gases and aerosols leaving the UK in gentle North Westerly airflow over the UK. The objective, in addition to measuring the export fluxes of pollutants is to derive the chemical processing (gas/aerosol partitioning & oxidation state) of the air mass.

Sortie Summary: The budget measurements will be obtained by flying off the South and East coasts along a coastal transect beginning in the Bristol Channel to sample background air off the coast of Cornwall. The transect of the UK outflow begins along the English Channel heading East to Dover then North to the point where airflow off the land stops, which according to current forecasts is North Yorkshire. Vertical profiles (50 – 6000 ft) once upwind in the Bristol channel and downwind of the source region off the S Scottish coast on the Southbound leg will provide the vertical structure in concentration and meteorology. These should clearly extend into the free troposphere (Mission Scientist to verify from profiles of humidity, temperature and CO. These measurements will establish the upwind concentration, the concentration differential at the top of the boundary layer and the concentration in the outflow from the source region. Flight ceiling will be 10000ft. Cabin pressure will be maintained at 1200ft, to minimize expansion of the Tedlar bags.

Sortie Detail with approx timing

- a) Take off Cranfield 09:00 and climb to 10000 ft for transit east to operating area. Destination waypoint 47 in the Bristol Channel; background filter run (sampling) & NO_x calibration.
- b) T+20: Upwind profile down to define the boundary layer structure off the coast with 1 min sampling at each height (6000, 4000, 2000, 500, 100, 50)
- c) T+35: Return to 1000 ft for sampling..
Start of filter run No 1. Start of Bag sampling (1 bag every min) continue all the way up the east coast. 30-minute filter pack runs from here (called by Mission Scientist)
- d) T+ 200 U-turn in front of Firth of Forth, downwind profile up (50, 100, 500, 2000, 4000, 6000).
- e) T+ 270 Land Cranfield

Crew List:

1. Pilot 1 - Alan Roberts
2. Pilot 2 – Ian Ramsay-Rae
3. CCM – Sue Angold
4. CCM2/Core Chemistry/TDLAS – Doug Anderson
5. Cloud Physics – Jim Crawford
6. Flight Manager – Alan Woolley
7. Mission Scientist – Eiko Nemitz
8. Filters - Paul James
9. Bag Sampling 1 – Debbie Polson
10. Bag Sampling 2 – Alison Perry
11. AMS – Hugh Coe
12. AMS Training – Gerard Capes
13. PTRMS – Anne Hulse

- Transit to Bristol Channel
- Profile down to point 37
- 48 50:50N 4:40W
- 46 50:01N 3:25W
- 45 50:01N 2:00W
- 44 50:40N 1:00W
- 43 50:40N 0:30E
- 42 51:05N 1:30E
- 41 51:53N 1:47E
- 40 52:41N 1:47E
- 39 52:00N 1:30E
- 80 54:05N 0:05E
- 79 50:00N 1:10W
- Next point N of 79?
- 79 50:00N 1:10W
- 80 54:05N 0:05E
- 39 52:00N 1:30E
- Cranfield

Wednesday 3 August 2005 00UTC ©ECMWF Forecast t+036 VT: Thursday 4 August 2005 12UTC
Surface: 2 metre temperature / 30 Metres Wind

Instrumentation strategies & issues:

Filter sampling: Filters will be taken throughout the flight. Filter pack 1 will contain a Teflon filter for trace metal analysis. Filter pack 2 will contain a Teflon prefilter (for major ion analysis), a nylon filter (for HNO₃ & HCl) and an acidified paper filter (for NH₃). Filters will be changed approximately every 30 minutes or when flight conditions change (as advised by the Mission Scientist). Filters are preloaded into

cartridges, which need to be handled with gloves and stored in sealed bags immediately. Filter sampling will be suspended during vertical profiles and resumed when FL10 is re-attained. During breaks, filter packs will be isolated by switching off the pump (to minimise evaporation of volatile aerosol components). During initial transfer to the operating area, a set of filters should be loaded into the filter packs, without sampling, to provide a blank value. Three 30-min runs of filters on each leg (S→N and N→ S)

AMS: The AMS will be operated continuously during the flight. Monitored masses will include m/z 16, 18, 28, 30, 43, 44, 46, 57 and 64. The inlet remains closed until airborne to minimize contamination during taxi take-off.

Core Chemistry: CO, SO₂, NO and NO₂ will be measured continuously during the flight. CO will be calibrated every 30 minutes at FL10.

Tedlar bags: Tedlar bags will be filled at a flow rate of 6 lpm, filling a bag over a duration of 30 s. Bags will be filled every 3 minutes upwind and every minute downwind of the source region and during each leveling out for a profile step. Bags should be filled to about 90% of their capacity to maximise sample volume. The cabin pressure will be tightly controlled. Bags from first part of flight can be stored in cargo hold for second part.

Aerosol & cloud physics: CN and PCASP are operated continuously.

Core meteorology & state: Are recorded as standard. Video recording of front facing and downfacing cameras.

PTRMS: Availability not yet confirmed.

TDL for CH₄ and CO₂: Operated by FAAM.

Quick-look data: pressure height, lat, long, temp, RH, CN, SO₂, NO, NO₂, O₃, CO, NO_{xy}(HNO₃)

The take off of this flight, originally scheduled for 9 am was delayed until 12 noon. The cause was that while an email had been sent to the CAA in time, the CAA office had not been staffed the previous afternoon and the notification of the flight plan had therefore not been published the previous evening. The CAA office (although notionally open from 8:30 am) was not staffed until 8:45 am on the morning of the flight. This appears to have been a one-off situation. In the future DirectFlight will check that the flight plan has been posted by the CAA in the morning. Although it would have been difficult to mend the situation, we would have been able to relax the power-up time of the aircraft.

The delayed start meant (a) that a band of rain approaching from the NW had advanced further to the SE and (b) that sea breeze effects were more likely to be encountered in the SE, where the wind speed was forecast to be lowest. Hence, the flight plan was revised compared with the original sortie. The flight commenced from Cranfield eastwards to the coast, flying a continuous descending profile on reaching the coast. The plane that followed the east coast northward, turned in front of the Firth of Forth and followed the GB coastline clockwise to the Isle of White. Here another U turn and profile was flown, before the plane left the coast at Great Yarmouth. The flight was flown with a reduced set of instrumentation (AMPEP without FLUXEX), i.e. no NO_x, PTRMS and only one filter pack (no metal analysis).

Plumes of all pollutants measured online were larger than on the previous day and in particular the plumes of Teeside and Edinburgh/Glasgow were similar on the north and the southbound legs. Due to the modified flight plan, less effort was available to characterize the background air. Although the forecast showed the air around of the Isle of White to represent Atlantic background air, concentrations here were still elevated and during the vertical profile layers of pollution were observed at higher altitudes, together with a decrease in wind speed with height. However, the wind direction at lower level was inconsistent with sea breeze effects. It is possible that the advancing frontal system led to the vertical wind shear. The concentrations measured N of the Edinburgh / Glasgow plume may represent the better background values for the flight.

SO₂ concentrations were elevated during the flight, even at high altitude, possibly indicating an offset in the zero of the SO₂ instrument. The on/off switch of the filter sampling pump broke during flight, but could still be operated. The pilots reminded Mission Scientist and Flight Manager to take greater care to be quiet and put people on hold, while the pilots are talking to air traffic control.

Mission Scientist's Log

 Flight No **B** 119

Date 04/08/05

Page 1 of 2

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
10:55	T/O				cloud base at ~ 2800 ft.
					(also cirrus high level) top at ~ 5200 ft.
10:05	FP Run 1	start		10:05-15	background stopped @ 1000ft see descent
11:12	FL 100		110	14 m/s	wed = 300°
11:10	high level				plane of SO ₂
	problem with				pump, switch for filters
	interrupt of				profile descent
10:32	start FP				Run 2 start
11:38		1000 ft			w = 11 m/s wed = 271°
11:34					SO ₂ & CN signals dropped out occasionally position also!
11:00	CCN spectrum				taken in NOx/CO plane
12:06	FP Run 3				start.
12:14					w = 8 m/s wed = 248°
12:10					step change in CO introduced by CO cal.
12:24					end of plane (Gleason!)
12:44:44	FP Run 4				start.
12:57					Visible plane. 10 ppt NOx.
13:11					CCN background on
13:15					13 m/s @ 280°
13:17					Grimsby / Southport & Trent / ^{valley} ford stations
13:19:45	FP Run 5				start
13:30					12 m/s @ 292°
13:58					wind backing 3 m/s @ 281°
13:59					start sunrise phase, sea picture

SWH switch.
Aircan
SO₂ baseline

signals ignored
Cooler on flight deck.

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. B119

Date: 04 AUG 05

Operator: Jim Crawford

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G.M.T. DRS Time	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
10:58:00											PCASP, 2D-P & 2D-C operating FFSSP, SID1 & SDID2 not operated Heaters on after T/O
11:16:00	60	0.09			0	0		0	0		6000ft start of descent – cloud tops
11:21:00	387	0.09			0	0		0	0		2000ft level – filter snag
11:27:39	261	0.09			0	0		0	0		Start run 1
11:29	371	0.09									End run 1 Profile 2 to 1000ft
11:30:00	195	0.08									Start run 2
11:32:00	191	0.08									
11:34:00	185	0.08									
11:37:00	210	0.09									
11:39:00	221	0.09									
11:41:00	201	0.08									
11:43:00	220	0.08									
11:45:00	213	0.08									
11:48:00	237	0.09									
11:50:00	231	0.08									
11:52:00	240	0.08									
11:54:00	176	0.08									
11:56:00	238	0.09									
11:58:00	217	0.09									
12:00:00	218	0.09									
12:02:00	214	0.09									
12:04:00	190	0.09									
12:06:00	189	0.08									
120800	151	0.08									
121000	133	0.08									
121200	187	0.09									

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. B119

Date: 4 aug 2005

Operator: Jim Crawford

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G.M.T. DRS Time	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
121400	211	0.08									
121600	166	0.08									
121800	153	0.08									
122000	204	0.08									
122200	140	0.08									
122400	91	0.09									
122433											Turn end of run 2
122635											Start run 3
123000	168	0.08									
123200	158	0.08									
123400	205	0.08									
123600	174	0.09									
123800	175	0.08									
124000	173	0.08									
124200	161	0.08									
124400	180	0.08									
124600	176	0.08									
124800	193	0.08									
125000	249	0.08									
125200	229	0.08									
125400	206	0.08									
125516	223	0.08						50		1	Light shower
125700	236	0.08						291		1	
125800	222	0.08									
130400	201	0.08									
130600	215	0.08									
130800	188	0.08									
131000	230	0.08									
131200	200	0.08									
131400	267	0.08									

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. B119

Date: 4 aug 2005

Operator: Jim Crawford

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G.M.T. DRS Time	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
131800	330	0.08									
132000	200	0.08									
132200	320	0.09									
132400	300	0.09									
132600	280	0.09									
132800	292	0.09									
133000	310	0.08									
133200	216	0.08									
133400	269	0.08									
133600	305	0.08									
133800	301	0.08									
134000	306	0.08									
134200	293	0.08									
134400	216	0.08									
134600	210	0.08									
134800	279	0.08									
135200	279	0.08									
135400	334	0.08									
135600	344	0.08									
135800	369	0.07									
140000	236	0.08									
140200	199	0.08									
140400	189	0.08									
140600	185	0.08									
140800	160	0.08									
141000	150	0.08									
141200	99	0.08									
141400	166	0.08									
141600	83	0.08									
141800	115	0.08									
142000	135	0.09									

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. B119

Date: 4 aug 2005

Operator: Jim Crawford

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G.M.T. DRS Time	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
142200	142	0.08									
142400	192	0.08									
142600	200	0.09									
142800	187	0.08									
143000	262	0.08									
143200	273	0.08									
143400	315	0.08									
143600	314	0.08									
143640											Descent to 100ft
143841	135	0.08									100ft start
143943	145	0.08									100ft end
											Profile to 5000ft
144421	102	0.08									Run at 5000ft
144700	94	0.08									
144900	87	0.09									PCASP structure in this run
145100	135	0.09									
145300	177	0.09									
145500	351	0.08									End run 5000ft
											Descent to 100ft
145700	713	1.73									3300ft
145900	692	2.74									1800ft
150019	277	2.25									Start run 6 1000ft
150200	329	1.75									
150400	322	1.73									

CCN LOG

ALLEVIATOR GMT ON	OFF	HEIGHT	TEMP INLET	STATIC					REMARKS
				1	2	3	4	5	
111050		24.3	24.3	1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5	S
				0.55	0.72	1.09	1.42	2.07	D
				639	739	754	926	1113	B
				651	702	691	673	670	R
				1994	1909	1905	1905	1890	P
				967.7	966.8	929.8	994.1	1005.	
113245		22.7 23.77	22.7	1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5	S
				0.49	0.71	1.09	1.40	2.1	D
				664	812	1042	1300	2227	B
				663	658	644	649	649	R
				1792	1790	1784	1781	1777	P
				1011.6	1011.3	1011.3	1011	1011	
114058		24.1	24.1	1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5	S
				0.50	0.72	1.05	1.4	2.08	D
				846	1148	1406	1708	2348	B
				652	646	646	648	652	R
				1770	1772	1772	1781	1779	P
				1011	1011	1011	1011	1011	
115130		24.05	24.05	1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5	S
				0.49	0.73	1.10	1.44	2.06	D
				734	982	1300	1418	1936	B
				652	655	651	651	651	R
				1768	1771	1781	1789	1787	P
				1011	1011	1011	1009.5	1009.5	
1201		24	24	1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5	S
				0.49	0.72	1.08	1.40	2.07	D
				724	734	868	1224	1022	B
				664	665	668	668	669	R
				1774	1778	1784	1783	1793	P
				1009.7	1008.6	1008.6	1008.5	1008	
121630		24	24	1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5	S
				0.49	0.71	1.07	1.4	2.11	D
				686	807	931	893	1214	B
				688	688	683	684	684	R
				1771	1780	1785	1795	1806	P
				1007.7	1007.6	1007.6	1007.6	1007.6	
1233				1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5	S
				0.47	0.74	1.13	1.41	2.03	D
				688	762	936	880	1442	B
				698	693	692	690	685	R
				1772	1778	1791	1795	1795	P
				1007.4	1007.4	1007.4	1007.4	1009	
1257				1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5	S
				0.50	0.71	1.06	1.41	2.06	D
				673	662	748	1016	1035	B
				714	710	704	715	715	R
				1776	1779	1787	1789	1800	P
				1010	1010.5	1011	1011	1011	

decreased
w height

Flight No. 15119 Route
 Date 4/8/05 Take Off 17:50
 Bag Samplers: Dakota Polson Alixen Perry
 Sheet No. 1

Bag Number	Time on (GMT)	Time off (GMT)	Lat	Lon	Comments
7103	11:03:20	11:03:50	52.5v	0.0E	10 kft
516	11:05:20	11:05:50			10 kft
1027	11:07:00	11:07:30			10 kft
223	11:09:00	11:09:30			
1001	11:11:00	11:11:30			
536	11:13:00	11:13:30			
262	11:15:00	11:15:30			
240	11:16:30	11:17:00			
893	11:17:30	11:18:00			Profile
268	11:18:35	11:19:05			
109	11:19:30	11:20:00			
85240	11:20:27	11:20:57			
260	11:21:30	11:22:00			
1016	11:22:35	11:23:05			
297	11:23:30	11:24:00			
517	11:24:20	11:24:50			
N/A.	11:25:05	11:25:35			Profile 100 ft.
542	11:25:50	11:26:20			
531	11:26:50	11:27:20			
534	11:27:40	11:28:10			
163	11:28:30	11:29:00			End of Run
133	11:29:25	11:29:55			Start of 1K run.
852	11:31:00	11:31:30			
36	11:32:00	11:32:30			
05-653	11:33:00	11:33:30			
1202	11:34:00	11:34:30			
05-248	11:35:00	11:35:30			
143	11:36:00	11:36:30			
234	11:37:00	11:37:30			
#234	11:38:00	11:38:30			
53	11:39:00	11:39:30			
235	11:40:00	11:40:30			
52	11:41:00	11:41:30			
118	11:42:00	11:42:30			
#62	11:43:00	11:43:30			
253	11:44:00	11:44:30			
242	11:45:00	11:45:30			
05-654	11:46:00	11:46:30			
1007	11:47:00	11:47:30			
287	11:48:00	11:48:30			
05-659	11:49:00	11:49:30			

11 16:33

Flight No. R119 Route
 Date 4/8/05 Take Off 12.00
 Bag Samplers: DEBBIE POLSON ALISON PERRY
 Sheet No. 2

Bag Number	Time on (GMT)	Time off (GMT)	Lat	Lon	Comments
9	11.50.00	11.50.30			
1024	11.51.00	11.51.30	54.5N	0.6W	
05-521	11.52.00	11.52.30			
05-182	11.53.00	11.53.30			
05- 1538	11.54.00	11.54.30			
207	11.55.00	11.55.30			
829	11.56.00	11.56.30			
58	11.57.00	11.57.30			
112	11.58.00	11.58.30			
271	11.59.00	11.59.30			
37	12.00.00	12.00.30	55N	1.1W	
97	12.01.00	12.01.30			
256	12.02.00	12.02.30			
61	12.03.00	12.03.30			
249	12.04.00	12.04.30			
44	12.05.00	12.05.30			
42	12.06.00	12.06.30			
160	12.07.00	12.07.30			
83	12.08.00	12.08.30			
250	12.09.00	12.09.30			
138	12.10.00	12.10.30			
300	12.11.00	12.11.30			
298	12.12.00	12.12.30			
05-273	12.13.00	12.13.30			
05-346	12.14.00	12.14.30			
05-307	12.15.00	12.15.30			
05-306	12.16.00	12.16.30			
05-365	12.17.00	12.17.30			
05-345	12.18.00	12.18.30			
05-192	12.19.00	12.19.30	56.1N	1.8W	
05-405	12.20.00	12.20.30			
05-361	12.21.00	12.21.30			
05-355	12.22.00	12.22.30			
05-374	12.23.00	12.23.30			
05-279	12.24.00	12.24.30			
05-277	12.25.00	12.25.30			
05-366	12.26.00	12.26.30			
05-303	12.27.00	12.27.30			Start of run 1000 ft.
05-358	12.28.00	12.28.30			
05-200	12.29.00	12.29.30			
05-351	12.30.00	12.30.30			

Flight No. Route

Date Take Off

Bag Samplers:

Sheet No.

Bag Number	Time on (GMT)	Time off (GMT)	Lat	Lon	Comments
05-519	12.31.00	12.31.30			
05-294	12.32.00	12.32.30			
31	12.33.00	12.33.30			
05-544	12.34.00	12.34.30			
05-440	12.35.00	12.35.30			
05-448	12.36.00	12.36.30			
05-556	12.37.00	12.37.30			
05-299	12.38.00	12.38.30			
05-341	12.39.00	12.39.30			
05-295	12.40.00	12.40.30	55.5N	14W	
05-320	12.41.00	12.41.30			
05-300	12.42.00	12.42.30			
05-479	12.43.00	12.43.30			
05-165	12.44.00	12.44.30			
05-195	12.45.00	12.45.30			
05-446	12.46.00	12.46.30			
05-463	12.47.00	12.47.30			
05-462	12.48.00	12.49.00			
05-534	12.49.10	12.49.40			
05-274	12.49.50	12.50.30			
05-258	12.51.00	12.51.30			
05-251	12.52.00	12.52.30			
05-313	12.53.00	12.53.30			
05-372	12.54.00	12.54.30			
05-298	12.55.00	12.55.30			
05-449	12.56.00	12.56.30			
05-412	12.57.00	12.57.30			
05-169	12.58.00	12.58.30			
05-276	12.59.00	12.59.30			
05-193	13.00.00	13.00.30			
05-167	13.01.00	13.01.30			
05-224	13.02.00	13.02.30			
05-469	13.03.00	13.03.30			
05-812	13.04.00	13.04.30			
05-294	13.05.00	13.05.30			
05-222	13.06.00	13.06.30			
05-296	13.07.00	13.07.30			
05-554	13.08.00	13.08.30			
05-417	13.09.00	13.09.30	54N	0.1E	Start
05-304	13.10.00	13.10.30			
05-357	13.11.00	13.11.30			

Flight No. Route

Date Take Off

Bag Samplers:

Sheet No.

Bag Number	Time on (GMT)	Time off (GMT)	Lat	Lon	Comments
05-368	13.12.00	13.12.30			
05-257	13.13.00	13.13.30			
05-480	13.14.00	13.14.30			
05-371	13.15.00	13.15.30			
05-481	13.16.00	13.16.30			
05-433	13.17.00	13.17.30			
05-419	13.18.00	13.18.30			
05-466	13.19.00	13.19.30			
05-289	13.20.00	13.20.30			
05-536	13.21.00	13.21.30			
05-356	13.22.00	13.22.30			
05-2785	13.23.00	13.23.30			
05-292	13.24.00	13.24.30			
05-171	13.25.00	13.25.30			
05-360	13.26.00	13.26.30			
05-445	13.27.00	13.27.30	S3.1N	1.1E	
05-324	13.28.00	13.28.30			
05-413	13.29.00	13.29.30			
05-373	13.30.00	13.30.30			
05-537	13.31.00	13.31.30			
05-497	13.32.00	13.32.30			
05-514	13.33.00	13.33.30			
05-447	13.34.00	13.34.30			
05-513	13.35.00	13.35.30			
05-283	13.36.00	13.36.30			
05-364	13.37.00	13.37.30			
05-150	13.38.00	13.38.30			
05-144	13.39.00	13.39.30			
05-515	13.40.00	13.40.30			
05-367	13.41.00	13.41.30			
05-560	13.42.00	13.42.30			
05-432	13.43.00	13.43.30			
05-465	13.44.00	13.44.30			
05-491	13.45.00	13.45.30			
05-426	13.46.00	13.46.30			
05-448	13.47.00	13.47.30			
05-472	13.48.00	13.48.30			
05-495	13.49.00	13.49.30	S1.8N	1.7E	
05-467	13.50.00	13.50.30			
05-416	13.51.00	13.51.30			
05-523	13.52.00	13.52.30			

Flight No. Route
 Date Take Off
 Bag Samplers:
 Sheet No.

Bag Number	Time on (GMT)	Time off (GMT)	Lat	Lon	Comments
05-240	13.53.00	13.53.30			
05-309	13.54.00	13.54.30			
05-437	13.55.00	13.55.30			
05-547	13.56.00	13.56.30			
05-404	13.57.00	13.57.30			
05-443	13.58.00	13.58.30			
05-553	13.59.00	13.59.30			
05-260	14.00.00	14.00.30			
05-423	14.01.00	14.01.30			
05-500	14.02.00	14.02.30			
05-348	14.03.00	14.03.30			
05-194	14.04.00	14.04.30			
05-239	14.05.00	14.05.30			
05-362	14.06.00	14.06.30			
05-316	14.07.00	14.07.30			
05-228	14.08.00	14.08.30			
05-148	14.09.00	14.09.30			
05-410	14.10.00	14.10.30			
05-531	14.11.00	14.11.30			
05-305	14.12.00	14.12.30			
05-020	14.13.00	14.13.30			
05-325	14.14.00	14.14.30			
05-227	14.15.00	14.15.30			
05-347	14.16.00	14.16.30			
05-414	14.17.00	14.17.30			
05-170	14.18.00	14.18.30			
136	14.19.00	14.19.30			
528	14.20.00	14.20.30			
257	14.21.00	14.21.30			
21	14.22.00	14.22.30			
504	14.23.00	14.23.30			
4	14.24.00	14.24.30			
293	14.25.00	14.25.30			
146	14.26.00	14.26.30	50.6N	0.2W.	
204	14.27.00	14.27.30			
93	14.28.00	14.28.30			
512	14.29.00	14.29.30			
255	14.30.00	14.30.30			
05-196	14.31.00	14.31.30			
1306	14.32.00	14.32.30			
73	14.33.00	14.33.30			End of run. 14.32

Flight No. Route

Date Take Off

Bag Samplers:

Sheet No.

Bag Number	Time on (GMT)	Time off (GMT)	Lat	Lon	Comments
232	14.34.00	14.34.30			
272	14.35.00	14.35.30			
90	14.36.00	14.36.30			
167	14.36.50	14.37.20			
293	14.37.35	14.38.05			
189	14.38.20	14.38.50			
1203	14.39.05	14.39.35			
202	14.39.50	14.40.20			
291	14.40.36	14.41.06			
43	14.41.20	14.41.50			
8	14.42.05	14.42.35			
158	14.42.50	14.43.20			
184	14.43.37	14.44.07			
35	14.46.00	14.46.30			
282	14.47.00	14.47.30			
292	14.48.00	14.48.30			
544	14.49.00	14.49.30			
05-197	14.50.00	14.50.30			
537	14.51.00	14.51.30			
128	14.52.00	14.52.30			
1011	14.53.00	14.53.30			
6	14.54.00	14.54.30			
243	14.55.00	14.55.30			
175	14.56.00	14.56.30			
45	14.57.00	14.57.30			Run (end of)
258	14.58.00	14.58.30			
281	14.59.00	14.59.30			
N/A.	15.00.00	15.00.30			Start of run. (6)
503	15.01.00	15.01.30			
115	15.02.00	15.02.30			
1012	15.03.00	15.03.30			
1010	15.04.00	15.04.30			
05-429	15.05.00	15.05.30			
111	15.06.00	15.06.30			
165	15.07.00	15.07.30			
1013	15.08.00	15.08.30			
5	15.09.00	15.09.30			
284	15.10.00	15.10.30			
198	15.11.00	15.11.30			
541	15.12.00	15.12.30			
209	15.13.00	15.13.30			

AMS PreFlight Setup/Cal Sheet v2.00

DATE: 04/08/05

FLIGHT: 8119

OPERATOR: GC

Time:	Action:	Location:	Yes/No:	Notes	Comments:	
Power ON	Ensure Inlet Closed	Inlet Valve	✓			
	Ensure Multiplier Off	Electronics box	✓			
	Ensure Heater Off	Electronics box	✓			
	Ensure all Pumps Off	Pump Control box	✓			
	Turn on 230V Breaker	Power unit on a/c wall	✓			
	Turn on:	Electronics box power Diaphragm pump power Turbo pump power CPC Power, both Buttons	Power distribution box	✓ ✓ ✓ ✓		
	Open backing pump valve	Front facing side of rack.	✓			
	Turn on Alcatel...100% speed	Pump Control Box, after #6	✓			
	Turbo pumps 2 and 3 ON...100%	Pump Control Box	✓	Monitor Pump Currents		
	Turbo pumps 4 and 5 ON...100%	Pump Control Box	✓			
	Turbo pump 6 ON...100%	Pump Control Box	✓			
	Plug in CPC fill bottle	Rear of CPC	✓			
Turn on heater	Electronics box	✓		Approx 2.8V, 0.9A		
Pre-Brief	Turn on Balzers Box	Power distribution box and Balzers box	✓			
	Turn on Copper	Electronics box	✓		Approx 125Hz	
	Turn on PC/Monitor	Power distribution box and PC	✓			
	Start AMS software	PC Desktop	✓			
	Turn autosaving off	Parameter menu, Averaging and saving tab	✓		NEGATIVE NUMBER	
	Reduce Multiplier voltage by 0.5kV	Parameter menu, Multiplier and chopper tab	✓			
	Set filament to 0.00mA, Scan range 0-300amu	Parameter menu, Mass Spectrometer tab	✓			
	Turn Multiplier on	Electronics box	✓			
	Turn filament on @0.05mA	MS mode, shift+B, click emission arrow	✓			

Power on 0500 land 1345
 Briefing 0700 debrief 1415
 Security 0815 power down 1545
 Doors close 0830
 Take off 0900

AMS PreFlight Setup/Cal Sheet v2.00

DATE: 04/08/05

FLIGHT: 8119

OPERATOR: GC

Time:	Action:	Location:	Yes/No:	Notes	Comments:
Post Brief	Increase Multiplier voltage by 0.5kV	Parameter menu, Multiplier and chopper tab	✓		
	Close Grimm valve	Inlet valve	✓		
	CPC in low flow	Shift+total on CPC display	✓		
	Check RF box, Tune if needed	Turn Tune Screw on RF Box for best hit	✓		
	Log CPC on AMS serial port 2	Parameter menu, Serial port tab	✓		
	Set mass range scan 0-300	Parameter menu, Mass Spectrometer tab	✓		
	Open AMS inlet	Inlet valve	✓		
	Increase filament to 2.5mA	MS mode, shift+B, click emission arrow	✓		
	Toggle chopper in MS mode	Press T within MS mode	✓		
	Check Airbeams and flows	Add m28 to m/z selection, Clean pin hole???	✓	F=1.9, AB approx 2.3MHz	F=1.9 AR=2.2
	Tune Balzers	Software	✓	Ensure no major changes	screen dump
	Electron Multiplier Cal	Software, select suitable point manually	✓	Gain approx 3e6	
	✓ Get tof masses for IE cal	Software, m/z selection, left click on row	✓	15, 16, 17, 30, 46*	left m28 in: repeated
	Set thresholds In tof mode	Left click "SP thresholds" in left border	✓	wait	
	Mass Range Cal	MS mode, Click Mass Calibration	✓		
	Add m28 to tof list	Software, m/z selection, left click on row	✓		
	Run in MS-TOF alteration	Software	✓	Check tof windows	
	IE cal after 200 particles	Shift+M while sampling, Calibrate, Save, Exit	✓	SMPS s=4.1, a=0.41, 350nm	
	Remove CPC butanol from aircraft	Rear of CPC	✓		
	CPC in high flow	Shift+total on CPC display	✓		
	→ Reconnect inlet and GRIMM	Inlet	✓		
	Set CPC port=0 in AMS software	Parameter menu, Serial port tab	✓	LOG CPC IN LABVIEW	
	Set PC time with Horace	Desktop plus internet explorer	✓		
	Set mass range scan	Parameter menu, Mass Spectrometer tab	✓		0 - 300
	Select tof masses to scan	Software, m/z selection, left click on row	✓	14, 16, 30, 43, 44, 46, 48, 57	
	Set thresholds In tof mode	Left click "SP thresholds" in left border	✓		
	Add m28 to tof list	Software, m/z selection, left click on row	✓		
	Set DC marker 3 pos=6200	Parameter menu, Averaging and saving tab	✓		
	Backup parameter file	C:\AMSV\AMSCODE\AMSMENU.prm	✓		
	Set save interval	Parameter menu, Averaging and saving tab	✓	0.5 minutes????	
	→ Reconnect inlet, Close AMS valve	Inlet	✓		
	Start CPC software	PC Desktop	✓		
General Alteration mode, Open Inlet	Software, Start after t/o	✓			

AMS Calibration Log Sheet v2.00

DATE: 04/08/05 FLIGHT: B119

OPERATOR: G.C

Tuning

TIME: 0645	Old	New	Typical
Def Inner	30	30	22
Def Outer	15	15	11
Heater Bias	-6.49	-6.55	-6.5
Focus	16.00	14.50	12.5
Extraction	226	228	220

TIME:	Old	New	Typical
Def Inner			22
Def Outer			11
Heater Bias			-6.5
Focus			12.5
Extraction			220

Multiplier Cal

Might have to tweak filament current and multiplier voltage in order to set thresholds in calibration!!!!
This is done in the parameter menu..... Multiplier and Chopper Tab

TIME: 0620	New	Typical
KV	2.425	n/a
KV Change	-0.075	0.025kV
Gain	2.79×10^6	3.00E+06
G used Change	0.83	1

TIME: 1603	New	Typical
KV	2.475	n/a
KV Change	0.050	0.025kV
Gain	2.96	3.00E+06
G used Change	1.06	1

Ionization Efficiency Cal

TIME: 0930	New	Typical
IE (NO3)	2.023×10^{-6}	2.00E-06
RIE (NH4)	3.803	4
IPP NO3	470	400
IPP NH4	519	550
Airbeam MS	2.07×10^6	2.20E+06
Airbeam TOF	1.24×10^6	2.00E+06
Run Number	4468	n/a

TIME: post flight	New	Typical
IE (NO3)	2.21	2.00E-06
RIE (NH4)	3.42	4
IPP NO3	514	400
IPP NH4	511	550
Airbeam MS	2.49	2.20E+06
Airbeam TOF	1.71	2.00E+06
Run Number	5031	n/a

4.85% nAMS / CPC

Filter Run

TIME:	1101
Run number	4468

TIME:	1536 → 1542
Run number	4996

AMS Diagnostic Log Sheet v2.00

DATE: 04/08/05 FLIGHT: B119

OPERATOR: G.C.

Time 1200

Pump #	I(A)	I (typical)	Speed (%)	Speed typical
1/Alcatel	0.9	0.86	89	98
2	3.42	3.5	100	100
3	1.38	1	100	100
4	0.59	0.5	100	100
5	0.41	0.4	100	100
6	0.43	0.46	100	100

	New	Typical
Heater V	2.83	2.5
Heater I	0.92	0.9
Heater T	589	580
Heater B	73.1	75V
Multiplier	2.43	n/a
Pressure	1.86	2 Torr

	New	Typical
I electronics	1	1A
I turbo	7.5	7A
I diaphragm	1.4	2A
MS AB	2.18	2.2Mhz
TOF AB	1.92	2Mhz
Flow	2.08	2

Time 1310

Pump #	I(A)	I (typical)	Speed (%)	Speed typical
1/Alcatel	0.89	0.86	89.5	98
2	3.42	3.5	100	100
3	1.38	1	100	100
4	0.57	0.5	100	100
5	0.41	0.4	100	100
6	0.43	0.46	100	100

	New	Typical
Heater V	2.83	2.5
Heater I	0.92	0.9
Heater T	590	580
Heater B	73.0	75V
Multiplier	2.43	n/a
Pressure	1.85	2 Torr

	New	Typical
I electronics	1.0	1A
I turbo	7.5	7A
I diaphragm	1.4	2A
MS AB	2.16	2.2Mhz
TOF AB	2.03	2Mhz
Flow	2.07	2

Time 1430

Pump #	I(A)	I (typical)	Speed (%)	Speed typical
1/Alcatel	0.90	0.86	89.4	98
2	3.43	3.5	100	100
3	1.38	1	100	100
4	0.60	0.5	100	100
5	0.41	0.4	100	100
6	0.43	0.46	100	100

	New	Typical
Heater V	2.84	2.5
Heater I	0.93	0.9
Heater T	591	580
Heater B	73.1	75V
Multiplier	2.43	n/a
Pressure	1.86	2 Torr

	New	Typical
I electronics	1	1A
I turbo	7.5	7A
I diaphragm	1.4	2A
MS AB	2.24	2.2Mhz
TOF AB	1.99	2Mhz
Flow	2.08	2

Time 1525

Pump #	I(A)	I (typical)	Speed (%)	Speed typical
1/Alcatel	0.90	0.86	89.48	98
2	3.41	3.5	100	100
1.35	1.38	1	100	100
4	0.58	0.5	100	100
5	0.41	0.4	100	100
6	0.44	0.46	100	100

	New	Typical
Heater V	2.85	2.5
Heater I	0.92	0.9
Heater T	592	580
Heater B	73.0	75V
Multiplier	2.42	n/a
Pressure	1.85	2 Torr

	New	Typical
I electronics	1	1A
I turbo	7.5	7A
I diaphragm	1.4	2A
MS AB	2.18	2.2Mhz
TOF AB	1.87	2Mhz
Flow	2.06	2

AMS PostFlight Setup/Cal Sheet v2.00

DATE: 04/08/05

FLIGHT: B119

OPERATOR: G.C.

Time:	Action:	Location:	Yes/No:	Notes	Comments:
Pre-land	Stop AMS,Grimm CPC logging	Software	✓		
	Close AMS inlet	Inlet	✓		
	Exit Labview		✓		
	Enable CPC in AMS software	Parameter Menu, Serial Ports tab	✓		
Post-land	Set CPC in Low Flow	Shift+totalizer on CPC display	✓		
	Open Inlet		✓		
	Turn off autosave (-ve number)	Parameter Menu,Averaging and saving tab	✓		
	Set mass range scan 0-300	Parameter menu, Mass Spectrometer tab	✓		
	Electron Multiplier Cal	Software, select suitable point manually	✓		Check gain at current V
	Get tof masses for IE cal	Software,mz selection,left click on row	✓		15,16,17,30,46*
	Set thresholds In tof mode	Left click "SP thresholds" in left border	✓		wait
	Mass Range Cal	MS mode, Click Mass Calibration	✓		
	Add m28 to tof list	Software,mz selection,left click on row	✓		
	Run in MS-TOF alteration	Software	✓		Check tof windows
	IE cal after 200 particles	Shift+M while sampling,Calibrate,Save,Exit	✓		SMPS s=4.1,a=0.41,350nm
	Attach Zero filter to inlet		✓		
	Select tof masses to scan	Software,mz selection,left click on row	✓		14,16,30,43,44,46,48,57
	Set thresholds In tof mode	Left click "SP thresholds" in left border	✓		
	Add m28 to tof list	Software,mz selection,left click on row	✓		
	General alteration,10 mins	Software, F3 to NonAutoSave	✓		Check tof windows
	Close inlet		✓		
Data	Copy AutoSaveData folder	Source C:\AMS\AMSDData\AutoSaveDate	✓		
		Dest C:\AMS\SAMSDData\Summer05\flight	✓		
	Copy NonAutoSaveData folder	Source C:\AMS\AMSDData\NonAutoSaveDate	✓		
		Dest C:\AMS\SAMSDData\Summer05\flight	✓		
	Copy AMSLogFiles folder	Source C:\AMS\AMSDData\AMSLogFiles	✓		
		Dest C:\AMS\SAMSDData\Summer05\flight	✓		
	Copy CPC data	Source C:\UCPC\	✓		
		Dest C:\AMS\SAMSDData\Summer05\flight	✓		
	Backup directory to DVD/laptop		✓		
	Delete AutoSaveData	Source C:\AMS\AMSDData\AutoSaveDate	✓		FILES ONLY, NOT FOLDER
Delete NonAutoSaveData	Source C:\AMS\AMSDData\AutoSaveDate	✓		FILES ONLY, NOT FOLDER	
Delete AMSLogFiles	Source C:\AMS\AMSDData\AutoSaveDate	✓		FILES ONLY, NOT FOLDER	
Delete CPC data	Source C:\AMS\AMSDData\AutoSaveDate	✓		FILES ONLY, NOT FOLDER	
ShutDown	Turn off Multplier & Balzers	Electronics box	✓		
	Turn off all Turbos and PC	Pump Controller Box	✓		
	Shut Backing Valve	Back of rack	✓		
	Turn off heater,chopper,the rest	Electronics box, then power unit and Breakers	✓		

High mp3 player.

→ "backed up" folder.

EGTC -> EGSC - Overview

NavData Cycle 2005-8 Expires: Thursday, 01 September 2005.

Scale: 1:2602424 (1 inch = 35.69 naut mi). Printed on 04 Aug 2005

JEPPESEN

FliteStar 9.140

Flight Manager's Instrument Status Log

Flight No. **B119**

Date: 04/08/05

Instrument	Fitted	Operated	Instrument	Fitted	Operated
<u>Navigation</u>			<u>Cloud Physics</u>		
INU		Y	Probes		
XR5M GPS		Y	FFSSP		N
Cruciform GPS	Y	N	PCASP		Y
Satcom C		Y	2D-P		Y
Satcom H		Y	2D-C		Y
<u>Thermometers</u>			Cloudscope	N	N
De-Iced Temp		Y	SID 1	Y	N
Non De-Iced		Y	SID 2	Y	N
Heimann	N		HVPS	N	
<u>Hygrometers</u>			CIP25	Y	N
G. Eastern		Y	CIP100	Y	N
J. Williams		Y			
Nevzorov		Y			
TWC		Y			
FWVS	Y	N	Racks:		
<u>Radiometers</u>			INC	Y	N
Upper Clear	Y	Y	CCN / CNC		Y
“ Red	Y	Y	CVI	Y	N
“ Silicon	Y	Y			
“ JO1D	Y	Y	<u>Aerosol</u>		
Lower Clear	Y	Y	PSAP	Y	N
“ Red	Y	Y	Nephelometer	N	
“ Silicon	Y	Y	Filters	Y	Y
“ JO1D	N		AMS	Y	Y
<u>Large Radiometers</u>					
TAFTS	N				
MARSS	N				
DEIMOS	N		<u>Others:</u>		
ARIES	N		NIR TDLAS	Y	Y
SWS	N		2BT O3	Y	N
<u>Chemistry</u>			VACC	Y	N
Ozone	Y	Y	PEROXIDE	Y	N
SO2	Y	Y	Formaldehyde	Y	N
NOX	Y	Y	ADA	Y	N
CO	Y	Y	CPI	Y	N
ORAC	Y	N	NOxy	Y	N
PAN	Y	N	PTRMS	Y	N
PERCA	N	N	Bag Sampling	Y	Y
WAS	Y	N			

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B119

Date: 04/08/05

Instruments

1. Filters pump switch sheared off
2. CCNC Rack - padding on aisle side falling off.
3. Horace display intermittently drops out, batches of dropouts around every 30 minutes.
4. Network connection on Filters laptop intermittent

Status of other instruments

CPI –
Cloud Physics –
NOxy –
CVI -

Aircraft

- 1.

Satcom H Calls -

Tephigramme on take-off:

Descent on hitting coast (interrupt at 2000 ft)

